

Some Problems of Effective Organization of the Training of Female Football Players in Sports Clubs

Dzhemilov Temur Rasimovich¹,

¹Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, The Department of "Physical Culture" is large teacher

Abstract:

In the article, the specific features that should be paid attention to in improving the physical fitness of female players, as well as the aspects that should be paid special attention to when giving them physical loads, are studied in detail. In this regard, the opinions of scientists who have conducted research are summarized and analyzed, and conclusions are given.

Keywords: physical fitness, women's organism, special features, physical development, sexual dimorphism, effectiveness of results, analytical methods.

INTRODUCTION

Decree PF 5368 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" and Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 "On measures to further develop football" - Decision 3610 created great opportunities for the field of physical education and sports of our country, including football officials of our country. In accordance with the implementation of these decisions and decrees, promising changes are being made in the sport of our country, especially football.

As the tasks of developing sports in our country and strengthening its position on the world scale are defined at the level of state policy, the issues of raising training and their effectiveness to new levels in each sport are required to be urgently resolved. In particular, paying special attention to the sport of football puts responsible tasks before specialists. Women's football is no exception.

As of today, women's football has begun to receive sufficient attention in our country. But at the same time, it should be noted that in order to bring training to the level of modern requirements, we

believe that great attention should be paid to the issues of carrying out purposeful and focused work, and most importantly, organizing training in a correct and rational manner.

The purpose of our pedagogical observation is to research the factors in the effective implementation of the training of female football players, to determine the factors affecting the training of female football players, to analyze the planning of training sessions, to determine the indicators that reflect the system of the training and competition process, and to carry out analytical work on their correlation. resolved.

Results of pedagogical observations. Based on the opinions concluded in sports theory, it should be said that it is important to provide training taking into account a number of factors when conducting training sessions with female athletes, especially female football players. One of the main aspects is to take into account women's ovarian-menstrual cycles when creating training mesocycles. The second case is the organization of training taking into account aspects such as the age of the athletes and the level of individual training.

MAIN PART

During our observation, there were training and competition activities of NavDPI sports club and NavDPI football club of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute. At the time of the pedagogical analysis, the analysis showed the disproportion between the indicators in the course of training and competition activities, that is, between the indicators of the development of the main technical and tactical actions performed by the athletes (in training) and their performance (in the competition). During the training, the proportion of time allocated to the development of the organizers of technical and tactical training did not fully correspond to the indicators of the competition activity system. This situation means that it is necessary to revise the time ratios planned for each of its organizers in technical-tactical training and carry out corrections in the planning work aimed at organizing training. It should be noted that there are significant differences between the training level and age of the girls playing in the team. These situations, in turn, should require an individual approach to the training of girls. But the analysis shows that the individual approach to sportsmen-girls in the training was carried out, usually only when they were sick or in the process of recovery after injuries. There is no attention paid to the individualization of the training, taking into account the level of technical-tactical, physical or tactical training of female football players. We think that in this case, the organization of training taking into account the age characteristics and the level of training will be one of the factors that help the training to be effective.

The analysis during the study also showed that there are shortcomings in the team's preparation planning training. In this regard, it is important to make clarifications in the planning of the training process, to develop training programs and work plans aimed at training female football players, taking into account the characteristics of the girls' body, developing control standards aimed at studying the levels of training, or necessarily applying the existing, scientifically based standards in practice in the training process. is one of the factors.

In conclusion, it should be said that the development of women's football in our country means that the process of their preparation should be improved. Every factor that affects the effective organization of the process must be taken into account, it should be developed and implemented based on appropriate regulatory documents, planning the distribution of hours in the planning of training types in accordance with the stages of long-term training, etc. remains one of the issues waiting for an urgent solution.

In order to develop women's football, it is necessary to form a girls' football school.

Of course, I believe that this is the goal of every club that sets a high goal for itself and every coach that sets a goal for itself. This requires the initiative of our coaches. All team coaches should

establish a women's football school under the club where they work, have a reserve from the school, and after a certain time a player will reach the main team, this is correct.

In fact, the biggest problem in women's football is the reserve. There is no such problem in men's football, they have many options. This is because they have U-21, U-18 and football schools. For example, if there are 240-250 players in the women's championship, there can be 100-150 highly experienced players. A simple example, if 5-6 girls in the club team will get married next year, we will have a problem to fill their place. The existence of a women's football school, and the systematic nature of these activities, will certainly depend on finances. I think it will only be useful if the UFA leadership makes this thing mandatory for each team and defines it in the regulations. Women's football will not stop. A player can play for 10 or 8 years. For men, a player can play from 20 to 35 years old, but the situation is different here. If someone plays in a good form for 3 years, he can get married the next year. We are also working on this. It is necessary to approach trainers responsibly in matters of training in sports.

In this regard, what should be done in connection with the formation of a women's football team in Uzbekistan.

In this regard, NavDPI sports club formed its women's football team in 2021. I believe that the women's football team is systematically organized on the basis of the training schedule. The current conditions in the NavDPI sports club show that they have a problem with the stadium, and there are also issues such as starting the work of 2-3 coaches. In addition, we have set ourselves the goal of supplying personnel to the regional women's national team. I don't know, maybe others are in action, but I covered the ones I know about in this article. I find this very sad. We are waiting for help from the management regarding the situation. We want to have a stadium that meets the standard. After all, we want our university students to play in our national team.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. 2018-yil 17-martdagi “Futbolni rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori.
2. Tolipjonov A.I. Yuqori malakali futbolchlar tayyorlashning zamonaviy tizimi. O‘quv qo‘llanma. – T.: O‘ZDJTvaSU. 2012. – B. 164.
3. Nurimov R.I. Yosh futbolchilarni texnik va taktik tayyorlash. T.: 2005 – B. 104.
4. Нуримов З.Р. Основание эффективных средств совершенствования групповых тактических действий квалифицированных футболистов. Т. 2004.
5. Karimov A.A., To‘laganov A.A. Yuqori malakali futbolchilarni musoboqa faoliyatida tezlikni aniqlovchi ayrim jihatlari // Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg‘ulotlari nazariyasi va uslubiyatining zamonaviy muommolari. – T.: 2015 – B. 250-251.
6. Nurimov R.I., Davletnuradov S.R. Yuqori malakali futbolchilarning guruh taktik harakatlarni takomillashtirish. O‘quv uslubiy qo‘llanma. – T.: 2014. – B. 51.